

A NOTE ON PARACHOR AND RESONANCE

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In a previous note (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 283) we have laid down the parachor conditions for resonance. On this basis, if a single bond and a double bond are interchanged, there is no change in parachor and hence resonance structure should consist of this exchange. Parachor thus explains the resonance structures of NO_2 group, NO_3 and CO_3 ions. It may be noted that dipole moment does not support resonance although electron diffraction measurements confirm it.

The acids, esters, amides and chlorides can also show resonance structure on the same ground. It is supported by the fact that they show none of the ketonic carbonyl reactions. Resonance structures of ozone, sulphur dioxide and sulphur trioxide are explained similarly from the parachor point of view. Resonance between various structures of Kekulé for benzene, naphthalene, anthracene and phenanthrene occurs for the same reason.

When a benzene ring changes to canoeical ring, a double bond disappears and two rings of four appear. This does not involve any change in parachor as the parachor of a double bond is equal to the parachor of two rings of four. Resonance between Kekulé's structure and Dewar's structure is thus possible. Glasstone ("Recent Advances in Physical Chemistry", 1938, p. 110) expresses a surprise that parachor values do not indicate resonance. He did not realise that the various resonance structures according to parachor condition should have the same parachor.

It will be seen that the parachor results do not directly give a clue to resonance, since parachor values for the various structures according to parachor condition of resonance should be the same. It indirectly suggests that if in a compound a rearrangement is possible such that the parachor value does not change appreciably, the resonance between these structures is possible. This happens when

- (i) a single and a double bond are interchanged,
- (ii) two double bonds are interchanged with a single bond and a triple bond,
- (iii) a benzene ring changes to canoeical ring with the disappearance of a double bond and appearance of two rings of four.

We have shown that majority of the known resonance structures fall under one of the three categories.

Our view explains certain anomalies. According to Thiel's rule butadiene should form the dibromo compound $\text{CH}_2\text{Br}.\text{CH}=\text{CH}.\text{CH}_2\text{Br}$. The main product, however (Thorpe and co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 729), is $\text{CH}_2\text{Br}-\text{CHBr}-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$. The first product assumes the resonance structure $\text{H}_2\text{C}^+-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2^-$. This according to our view is not possible, since it involves a change in parachor of 23.2 units.

The resonance structures for isocyanide group and CO are suggested (Glasstone, "Recent Advances in Physical Chemistry", 1938, p. 115). According to us this is not possible as it involves a change in parachor of 23.2 units. Our view is supported by dipole moment and Raman effect and these groups have one structure, mainly $\text{C}^+ \equiv \text{N}^-$ and $\text{C}^- \equiv \text{O}^+$.